

Any software written in memory-insecure languages potentially contains some bugs. They can be either the result of poor-quality programming and design flaws, or the result of special additions to the code of open-source projects.

Estimating the number of bugs is difficult due to the diversity of each project's source code and the unclear definition of what is and is not a bug. Different sources give different quantitative data on the average value of errors per thousand lines of code.

It is not the specific number of errors that is important, but their presence. Not every error can be exploited. However, even one single error, lost from the eyes of developers in millions of lines of source code of a large project, can be successfully used by attackers to intercept control of the system and then execute malicious code.

Programming errors or special bookmarks are especially dangerous due to the fact that a huge number of digital systems simultaneously work with identical software and can be attacked en masse.

Identical executable files of the most popular software run on millions of computers. This facilitates large-scale exploitation; the same attack successfully hits many targets.

Diversifying transformations are those transformations that change the internal structure of a program in such a way as to obtain a large number of different copies of it, different from each other, but functionally equivalent.

A diversified population is a set of different copies of a program obtained through diversifying transformations. Diversifying transformations allow you to get away from the monotony of software.

The requirement that a programming language's memory model must provide reasonable guarantees to the programmer sounds extremely informal. Let's try to formulate it more specifically.

Obviously, the programmer must have an idea of how the program he is working on behaves, and the behavior of the program is precisely determined by the memory model. As a consequence, it is desirable that the memory model be as simple and understandable as possible, and that there be formal tools for reasoning about programs within the model.

Simplicity is a very subjective criterion, especially when comparing weak memory models, whereas the availability and expressive power of analysis tools can be used to more accurately compare models.

There are various methods for analyzing programs. Among them, it is worth noting the methods of model checking and Hoare logic verification.

There are also works devoted to weak memory models. The latter notes that if the memory model allows scenarios for the behavior of programs with the so-called. "out-of-thin-air values" (OOTA), then a class of properties that can be checked or proven for programs within such models is significantly limited. In particular, the C/C++11 memory model allows such scenarios.

What are "meanings out of thin air"? Unfortunately, at the moment there is no exact definition, but there is a set of examples of such behaviors, as well as the following sign of the presence of "meanings out of thin air".

If in a script for the behavior of a program in which there are no arithmetic expressions, a certain value appears (for example, this value is assigned to a variable or written to memory), and this value does not appear explicitly in the text of the program, then such a script has “meanings out of thin air.”

Scenarios of behavior with “meanings out of thin air” always have some cyclic dependence between the values found in them. The fact that some models allow such scenarios is usually the result of the fact that the approach chosen to specify the model makes it difficult or impossible to disable “out of thin air” values without disabling the desired optimizations.

Recently, automatic detection of errors in program code has become an integral part of the modern software development process. To increase the safety and reliability of programs, you need to find and eliminate as many errors as possible, preferably in the early stages of development.

For search, as a rule, a set of analysis and testing methods is used, complementing each other - static and dynamic program analysis, deductive verification, fuzzing, penetration testing.

Buffer overflow is a situation that occurs during program execution as a result of accessing an array at an index that has a negative value or exceeds the size of the buffer itself.

This error is especially critical in the C and C++ languages: an unpleasant feature of errors when working with memory in these languages is that the occurrence of such an error often does not lead to immediate consequences (such as, for example, crashing the program or generating an exception).

On the one hand, this makes it difficult to test and debug programs, because Observed anomalies in program behavior may appear much later than the actual occurrence of the error (or may not appear at all).

On the other hand, the presence of such a defect can lead to the appearance of an exploitable vulnerability in the program, allowing an attacker to cause a denial of service, gain access to sensitive data, and even seize control of the attacked device.

In C, array access is defined as dereferencing a pointer to one of the array's elements. The pointer value is calculated as an offset relative to the address of one of the elements (or the address immediately following the end of the array) by a certain number of elements.

Moreover, according to the language standard, if the calculated pointer does not contain the address of one of the array elements (goes beyond the boundaries), then dereferencing such a pointer will lead to undefined behavior.

Thus, to determine such an error, the analysis tool is faced with the task of determining for each dereference point the size of the array and the value of the pointer offset relative to the beginning of this array.

Based on this, the study of C-family programs in the context of information security is of particular interest due to the presence of a wide class of software defects associated with manual processing of memory objects.

An attacker could exploit errors in the handling of memory objects, which could lead to the compromise of sensitive data, injection of executable code, or denial of service.

Programs written in the C family of programming languages are also subject to typical classes of vulnerabilities inherent in programs written in other programming languages, for example, errors in processing input data or the use of programming interfaces considered unsafe.

According to the C++ programming language standard, undefined is the behavior of a program for which this standard does not impose any restrictions. The C++ programming language standard also states that the outcome of a program that causes undefined behavior is unpredictable.

Thus, the result of executing an incorrectly formed program completely depends on the strategy for implementing the translation of the program code of the C++ programming language compiler, as well as on the environment settings of this compiler and the target program execution environment.

The C++ programming language standard defines a set of incorrect language and semantic constructs that lead to undefined program behavior. A number of such constructions, in practice, do not lead to the manifestation of undeveloped software capabilities or can be corrected by the compiler automatically.

In particular, such constructs include program modules written in files without a newline character at the end of the file, or declaration of user declarations or definitions in the standard `std` namespace (with the exception of certain cases, such as specialization of template types or functions).

However, some of the language constructs that lead to undefined program behavior are translated into binary code, which leads to runtime errors.

The class of potential errors that can be identified through textual analysis of program code in combination with analysis of the binary image of the program includes software defects in the program code that arise as a result of potentially unsafe optimizing transformations used by the compiler.

In this case, it is advisable to carry out automatic analysis using mechanisms for mapping source program code to the resulting machine code, for example, using specialized preprocessor directives or debugging information.

Moreover, according to the language standard, if the calculated pointer does not contain the address of one of the array elements (goes beyond the boundaries), then dereferencing such a pointer will lead to undefined behavior.

Thus, to determine such an error, the analysis tool is faced with the task of determining for each dereference point the size of the array and the value of the pointer offset relative to the beginning of this array.

Based on this, the study of C-family programs in the context of information security is of particular interest due to the presence of a wide class of software defects associated with manual processing of memory objects.

An attacker could exploit errors in the handling of memory objects, which could lead to the compromise of sensitive data, injection of executable code, or denial of service.

Programs written in the C family of programming languages are also subject to typical classes of vulnerabilities inherent in programs written in other programming languages, for example, errors in processing input data or the use of programming interfaces considered unsafe.

According to the C++ programming language standard, undefined is the behavior of a program for which this standard does not impose any restrictions. The C++ programming language standard also states that the outcome of a program that causes undefined behavior is unpredictable.

Thus, the result of executing an incorrectly formed program completely depends on the strategy for implementing the translation of the program code of the C++ programming language compiler, as well as on the environment settings of this compiler and the target program execution environment.

The C++ programming language standard defines a set of incorrect language and semantic constructs that lead to undefined program behavior. A number of such constructions, in practice, do not lead to the manifestation of undeveloped software capabilities or can be corrected by the compiler automatically.

In particular, such constructs include program modules written in files without a newline character at the end of the file, or declaration of user declarations or definitions in the standard `std` namespace (with the exception of certain cases, such as specialization of template types or functions).

However, some of the language constructs that lead to undefined program behavior are translated into binary code, which leads to runtime errors.

The class of potential errors that can be identified through textual analysis of program code in combination with analysis of the binary image of the program includes software defects in the program code that arise as a result of potentially unsafe optimizing transformations used by the compiler.

In this case, it is advisable to carry out automatic analysis using mechanisms for mapping source program code to the resulting machine code, for example, using specialized preprocessor directives or debugging information.

If the source code is unavailable, automation of the analysis of this class of potential errors can be carried out using tools for analyzing binary images of programs with the participation of an analytical group that determines the rules for automatic detection of typical representatives of this class of software defects.

The C++ programming language standard declares that translation of program code is carried out "as is" (the as-if rule), that is, it should not change the observed behavior of the program.

Thus, the optimizing compiler can carry out any optimizing transformations of the program code that do not change the visible behavior of the program. Therefore, an optimizing compiler can apply dead code removal transformations to function calls that do not change the external behavior of the program.

The dead code removal transformation eliminates all instructions that do not affect the operation of the function. When transforming assembler into REIL representation, many instructions are created, the result of which is not used.

Removing dead code has several benefits: it reduces the size of the function and allows other types of analysis to avoid processing unnecessary instructions, thereby reducing the time of other types of analysis. After the transformation, a new function and a new control flow graph are created.

A popular use of assembler is program optimization, i.e. reduction in program execution time compared to high-level languages. But if you simply rewrite the text, for example, from C into

assembly language, translating each command in the most obvious way, you often find that the C procedure runs faster.

The optimization problem is usually divided into three main levels:

1) selection of the most optimal algorithm - high-level optimization; 2) the most optimal implementation of the algorithm is mid-level optimization; 3) counting the clock cycles spent on executing each command and optimizing their order for a specific processor - low-level optimization.

In particular, these include the C standard library function `memset`, which is a pure function, that is, deterministic and has no side effects.

One practical use of the `memset` function is to fill a data buffer containing sensitive information (such as the value of a cryptographic key or the result of a cryptographic convolution function) with a deterministic value after it has been used.

However, since the `memset` function is pure, if the target data buffer is not used further, the optimizing compiler can eliminate the `memset` function call construct. Such optimization is carried out, in particular, by the GCC and Clang compilers, as well as other optimizing translators, for example MSVC.

In this case, an attacker can use memory region inspection techniques using other vulnerabilities in the software system to gain access to buffer data containing confidential information, which can lead to compromise of such data.

It should also be mentioned that the C11 programming language standard defines a standard library function called `memset_s` to securely populate a data buffer containing sensitive information.

Programs that incorrectly process user data in terms of contract programming statements should be considered potentially vulnerable.

Anti-malware methods should include file access control.

MS Windows uses discretionary access control, namely a method based on setting access attributes.

Access control (limitation) is carried out by the central element of the security system - the access manager, which intercepts all requests to objects identifying subjects, access objects and parameters of the subject's requested access to the object (reading, writing, executing, etc.), providing based on the initially specified rules the subject's requested access, or denies it.

To set access rules, each object is assigned access attributes, indicating which subjects and what (with what parameters) access to them is allowed/denied.

When an access request is made, the dispatcher, receiving the necessary accounting information from the request, reads the attributes belonging to the object to which access is requested and, based on their analysis, determines the correctness of the request being processed. At the same time, it records information in audit logs about access.

Also monitors operating system objects running in a virtual machine.

The more information there is about the environment in which work is carried out, the more effectively it can be analyzed and protected.

Depth of information is a fundamental benefit of a concept called virtual machine introspection. VM introspection is the study of the current state of the VM at the system level.

For virtual machine introspection, the current state can be defined quite broadly, including information about processor registers, memory, disk, network, and any other events.

The fundamental problem of introspection of virtual machines is the gap in the levels of representations, the so-called semantic gap.

In other words, introspection is the extraction of data from the operating system that is used by the system for its operation, this data is hidden from the user.

The technical component is a set of software functions and algorithms that provide the analytical component with data for analysis. These can be, for example, the byte code of a file, text lines inside a file, a single program action within the operating system, or a whole chain of such actions.

The analytical component is a decision-making system that includes an algorithm that analyzes the data at its disposal and makes a certain judgment about it.

In accordance with this judgment, the antivirus (or other security software) takes the actions established by its security policy: notifies the user; sends a request for further action; quarantines the file; blocks unauthorized program actions, etc.

Modern anti-virus protection tools, as a rule, simultaneously implement both technical and analytical components, based on the combination of the listed protection methods.

At the same time, despite the fact that the signature method is outdated, it still remains in security products and is advertised, since it is part of a sustainable business model, and users are also accustomed to it.

However, do not forget that creating signatures is a manual process, so developing new signatures and releasing updates to the user can take from several hours to a day.

Thus, we find that signature mechanisms do not protect against new threats that have not yet entered the database. Due to the manual compilation of signatures, they give false positives. The database of signatures is growing day by day, and, in connection with this, working with signatures imposes increasing costs on computer resources.

As practice shows, the heuristic method copes only in a small number of cases, so this approach also does not solve the problem of protection against the launch of malicious programs.

With modern methods of hiding and encrypting executable files (for example, code obfuscation), it is almost impossible to detect new threats using such methods. The described methods are used in modern antivirus products.

Thus, by observing these, and not only, rules, you can make the system more secure.